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The pride of Kazakhstan-Al-Farabi Kazakh National University

Omarova Batish, Tlepbergen Akmoldir, Lecturers of KazNU Al-Farabi Kazakh National University

Abstract. The most renowned University in Kazakhstan is, without doubt, Kazakh National University. It has gained prestige and authority among all youth in the country. Its history is rich and has many advantages. The authors briefly outline the benefits and what it offers.

Key words: Kazakhstan, University, education, students

Kazakh National University named after al-Farabi (or KazNU) has long standing traditions and boasts many years of experience in scientific research, which is famous in the post-Soviet space. Nowadays, KazNU is a leading institution in the system of higher education of the Republic of Kazakhstan, which is the first one to pass international accreditation on all specialities and levels.

KazNU is a top university in the General Rating of universities of Kazakhstan. It is the first laureate of the President Award "For achievements in the field of quality". The university is awarded the Commonwealth of Independent States' diploma for achieving high quality products and services. KazNU is a member of the International Association of universities and co-founder of the Eurasian Association of universities. The institution was one of the first universities of Kazakh and Central Asia countries, which signed the Great Charter of Universities in Bologna, and successfully passed international certification for quality management system and got certificates of the world's largest certification centres, for instance, of the International certification system IQNet. The university has the goal to train and educate highly qualified professionals who will be competitive in the domestic and international labour market. Integration of achievements of modern science into the educational process is one of the directions of the further development. For this purpose courses, which are closely connected with applied science, are included into the training process. For example,

there are courses for students and postgraduates, which are developed according to results of scientific researches that were financed by the state because of their actuality. Autonomy of the university allows developing and changing curriculum according to requests of employers in order to increase practical skills of graduates. Moreover, the educational process is quite close to the international standards of education, for instance, curriculum and programs of the world's leading universities are used as a basis. Furthermore, each speciality has its own direction based on international ratings.

KazNU has a great educational, scientific, innovative and productive potential, which is used to prepare highly qualified specialists, further integration into international educational space, development of basic and applied researches and their implementation in practice. Results of scientific research are successfully implemented, for instance, by using in the production or manufacture. Many scientific groups have contracts with large domestic and international enterprises and according to the agreements they work on developing technology and production.

Nowadays, KazNU is educational and scientific complex offering wide range of specialities. There are 14 faculties, 98 departments, 20 scientific institutions and centres, a Technical Park. More than two thousand professors and doctors, more than 100 academicians of the largest academies, more than 30 laureates of Government and other awards, 40 laureates of awards for young scientists and 45 holders of State's research fellowships work in the university. There are more than eighteen thousand students and postgraduates. The university cooperates and collaborates with 418 large international universities on the issues of implementation of collaborative international educational programs, student exchange and more.

It can be said with confidence that KazNU shapes the future of Kazakhstan as most graduates represent the elite of Kazakh society and take part in the development of the country. Much attention is paid to social projects and programs as a form of financial help and motivation for students. For example, excellent students can get a 15% discount or there are large discounts for orphans or disabled students, for prize-winners of republican and international competitions. Possibility of participation in scientific projects offers another significant opportunity for younger generation.

As a result, they get experience and salary. The university also pays attention to the quality and conditions of buildings and accommodations for students. For example, a new 9-floor students' dormitory was built last year. It is well equipped and has access to the internet.

Studying at the university is a dynamic and fascinating experience. The younger

generation is actively involved in cultural life of the country, as the university has its own radio and TV programs, student clubs and societies under the Youth Organizations Committee of KazNU.

KazNU is one of the best universities in Kazakhstan with excellent infrastructure and a large number of highly qualified professors and teachers who effectively train and teach a lot of students working, studying and living in dynamic and exciting atmosphere.

KazNU is the oldest classical university of the Republic established by the Decree of the Kazakh Regional Committee (KRC) office dated November 13, 1933. One year after Kazakhstan's 1990 declaration of independence, the name was changed to Al-Farabi Kazakh State University. In 2001, the government classified it as a "national" university. More than 20000 students, graduates and PhD students study at KazNU, and there are more than 2500 faculty members working at KazNU, including 400 doctors of science, professors and more than 800 candidates of science and associate professors. Like other universities founded under the Soviet system, it is highly centralized.

The University has its own campus, the so-called "Kazgugrad", on the land between Timiryazev Street, Al-Farabi Avenue, the "Yessentai" ("Vesnovka") river, and the Botanical Garden. The main building (GUK) is 15 storey tall and hosts the administration and the History, Economics, Law, Philology and Journalism faculties. Al-Farabi Kazakh National University has the largest campus in Kazakhstan with a total area of 100 hectares in one of the most beautiful places of Almaty. The education infrastructure of the campus consists of 13 education buildings with a total area of 165 000 m² and scientific laboratories with a total area of 18 940 m².

There are 10 dormitories on campus and three more faculties: Geography, Biology, Preparatory and International Relations.

The departments of Physics, Mechanics-Mathematics, Chemistry were primarily located in the city. But in 2011 they moved to the newly constructed buildings on campus.

January 15, 1934 is the day of the official opening of Kazakh State University, which was established at the basis of the Pedagogical Institute by the decree of the Council of Peoples' Commissars of USSR and VKPb Kazakh regional committee. On December 2 of the same year KazSU was named after the famous Soviet party and state leader S.M. Kirov.

In January 1934, the first entrance exams at the faculties of Biology, Physics and Mathematics were held; in September they were held at the Faculty of Chemistry.

In 1937, the first Faculty of Humanities – the Faculty of Foreign Languages was established; a year later, the Faculty of Philology. In May 1941, as a result of joining with the University of the Kazakh Communist Institute of Journalism the Faculty of Journalism was established.

After the severe years of war, new faculties began to open. In August 1947, the Faculty of Geography was established, and in 1949 the faculties of Philosophy and Economics. As a result of the joining with the Alma-Ata Institute of Law in 1955, the Faculty of Law was established.

During the same period a strong scientific educational and methodological base emerged at the university. By the mid-1980s there were 98 departments, 43 scientific research laboratories and 9 scientific research groups at KazSU. The faculty staff consisted of 1180 people; among the faculty staff there were 30 academicians and AS KazSSR correspondent members, more than 100 doctors, professors, more than 600 science candidates, lecturers. Human resources were trained on 21 specialties and 74 specializations.

History of Kazakh National University. Al-Farabi is rich in a variety of scientific and educational events and public life, it is impregnated with enthusiasm and wisdom of young teachers, powerful energy of knowledge and power of scientific thought. Creativity and painstaking daily work of many generations of students, teachers and scientists on particles composed glorious destiny of the country's first university.

Al-Farabi Kazakh National University was the first university in Kazakhstan that entered into the International Association of Universities in the new historical conditions, to actively cooperate with foreign colleagues in the field of education and science of Turkey, Iran, China, South Korea, Egypt. From 1992-1993 academic year, the university began to work on the transition to the two-stage system of training. Al-Farabi Kazakh National University Students' Palace was named after the rector Dzholdasbekov. For the great merits of Al-Farabi Kazakh National University in the field of education and science also its enormous prestige in the world Association for the Promotion of Industry it was awarded with "Gold Medal SPI» in 2002. On September 16, 2003 in Bologna (Italy) in the walls of the old European University by the Great Charter of Universities was signed.

September 8, 2004 President of the Republic of Kazakhstan N.A Nazarbayev and President of the Czech Republic Vaclav Klaus took part in the festivities dedicated to the 70th anniversary of the Kazakh National University named after Al-Farabi laid the foundation stone for the future of the Scientific Library of the University.

Al-Farabi Kazakh National University became the largest, internationally recognized center for research and education that trains personnel for the competitive dynamic of Kazakhstan and other countries. In the general ranking of Kazakhstan and foreign universities Treasury it has already become a recognized leader!

The construction of new school buildings such as chemical, physical faculties and the unique Museum, the exhibition of which is devoted to the development of higher schools in the country.

Lecture of the president "Kazakhstan in the post-crisis world: intellectual breakthrough to the future" October 13, 2009 was the culmination of a momentous 75th anniversary of country's leading universities. "Kazakhstan needs an intellectual revolution, which will awaken and realize the potential of our nation," - said he. Priority role in the implementation of quality training by international standards, raising the scientific potential of Kazakhstan in the modern world is just right for Kazakh National University.

Treasury of the first among the educational institutions have been the winner of the Prize of the President of the Republic of Kazakhstan "For achievements in quality" (2006), member of the International Association of Universities and Eurasian leader of innovative development of higher vocational and postgraduate education and science, has repeatedly reaffirmed at the international level implementation of QMS (2008 – 2011).

Currently, there are more than 20,000 students the university enrolled, and over 1,500 teachers respectively. Among staff there are 27 academicians of the National Academy of Sciences, Academician of the International Academy of 6 high schools, 300 doctors and professors and 700 associate professors and candidates. Around 70 laureates of state individual and youth awards are working in the University too. Al-Farabi Kazakh National University is the only University in Kazakhstan which adopted the program of the United Nations "Academic Impact", and the results known rating agencies QS (UK), Thomson Reuters (USA) the university is among the first universities in Central Asia came to the rank of the most famous universities in the world (2011).

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